

***N,N'*-Dipyridylthiourea as a new sensitive reagent for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of osmium(VI) and iridium(III)**

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N,N'-Dipyridylthiourea (DPyT) reacts with Os^{VI} and Ir^{III} forming coloured extractable complexes (λ_{\max} 355 nm in chloroform : ethanol for Os complex and 335 nm for Ir complex in the same extractant). In presence of moderate excess of diverse ions both Os and Ir can be determined with DPyT in ppm level. The molar extinction coefficient and Sandell's sensitivity values for Os^{VI} and Ir^{III} complexes are 3.05×10^4 , 0.006 and 1.89×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.01 μ g cm⁻², respectively. The Os and Ir complexes have 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 M : R stoichiometries respectively.

Spectrophotometric methods are specially useful for the determination of osmium and iridium because of their very low occurrence. Many sophisticated and costly instruments like flame atomic absorption¹, inductively coupled plasma emission spectra also unable to determine these elements precisely without prior preconcentration or rigorous chemical separation when they are in ppm level. So in this communication, *N,N'*-dipyridylthiourea was introduced as a new chelate forming agent for both of these metals and served as a simple and cost effective spectrophotometric method for the determination of Os and Ir. Thiourea is a good reagent for Os² and some recently introduced reagents are also reviewed³, but *N,N'*-dipyridylthiourea has some advantages as regards the stability, simplicity, reproducibility and sensitivity of the method are concerned.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of green Os^{VI} complex show λ_{\max} at 355 nm and the yellow iridium complex at 335 nm against the reagent blank. Both the complexes are extractable in chloroform : ethanol mixture (4 : 1) and stable for more than 24 h.

The suitable range of pH for the complete extraction of Os-DpyT and Ir-DpyT are calibrated by adjusting the pH of the solution with sodium acetate and dil. HCl buffer. The absorbances are measured and the pH values of the aqueous layers are determined immediately after the extraction. The results indicate that the most suitable pH range for Os-DPyT complex is 3.6–5.8 and for Ir-DpyT complex the range is 5.0–6.4. At those pH ranges, stable complex formation as well as complete extraction is possible.

The results of extraction coefficient and degrees of

extraction of the Os-DpyT and Ir-DpyT complexes into various solvents indicate that osmium can be quantitatively extracted with *N,N'*-dipyridylthiourea when chloroform or ethyl acetate is employed as extractant. The addition of ethanol, 20% of the organic phase (chloroform) facilitates the extraction of the metal chelate in a single step. The Ir-DPyT complexes can also be quantitatively extracted with chloroform-ethanol mixture in 4 : 1 ratio.

The empirical formula of the osmium-DPyT and iridium-DPyT complex were determined by mole-ratio method and verified by slope-ratio method. It is observed that the reagent forms 1 : 2 metal : ligand complex with Os^{VI} and 1 : 3 metal : ligand complex with Ir^{III}. These are also corroborated with the IR data interpretation⁴ of the solid complexes.

Os^{VI} complex : The IR spectrum of solid Os-DPyT complex shows that the ligand band at 1500–1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic moiety) is shifted by 15–30 cm⁻¹ and also the ligand band at 760 cm⁻¹ (pyridine deformation) is shifted by 15 cm⁻¹ in complex. So the aromatic moiety is involved in coordination. The ligand band at 1470–1435 cm⁻¹ (amide-II) is shifted by 10 cm⁻¹ in the complex, which suggests the complexation through nitrogen. Again the ligand band at 1310 cm⁻¹ is shifted to 1300 cm⁻¹ in the complex and the band at 1350 cm⁻¹ stands same. The bands at 1140, 1185 cm⁻¹ (C=S corresponding to amide I)⁴ is shifted and merged in the complex indicating complexation through sulfur atom of the ligand. So we can assume that Os^{VI} is coordinating through sulfur atom and amide nitrogen or it may be in resonating form of another which may coordinate through pyridine ring and bonding through sulfur.

Ir-DpyT complex : The IR spectrum of the solid Ir-DpyT complex reflects the band at 1500–1600 cm⁻¹ (pyridine)

like the original ligand. The ligand band at 1470–1435 cm^{-1} (amide II) is shifted by 10–15 cm^{-1} in the complex, suggesting the coordination through NH nitrogen. The ligand bands at 1140, 1185 cm^{-1} assigned (C=S corresponding to amide I) band are shifted in complex by 5–10 cm^{-1} , suggesting the complex formation through sulfur atom.

So the structure of the iridium and osmium complexes are in agreement with the stoichiometry of the metal-DPyT complexes.

Molar absorptivity, sensitivity and optimal concentration range :

The molar absorptivity of Os^{VI} and Ir^{III} complexes, measured at 355 and 335 nm respectively are 3.05×10^4 and $1.89 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. According to Sandell's⁵ notation, the sensitivity of the colour reaction for osmium and iridium are 0.006 and 0.01 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The optimal concentration range for absorbance between 0.2 and 0.7 was 1.25–4.37 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for osmium complex and 2.05–7.17 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for iridium complex.

From an identical set of five experiments under optimal conditions, the relative mean error, the standard deviation and coefficient of variation for the determination of Os^{VI} (75.0 μg) and Ir^{III} (76.6 μg) with *N,N*-dipyridylthiourea have been found to be 0.96%, 0.96% and 1.28% for Os^{VI} complex and 0.36%, 0.40% and 0.52% for the Ir^{III} complex.

Effect of foreign ions : The tolerance limits for interferences, i.e. up to which concentration the error does not exceeds $\pm 2\%$, in the determination of 100.0 μg of Os^{VI} and 102.2 μg of Ir^{III} are as follows : V^{VI} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{III} , Ni^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} , Sb^{III} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} at 500-fold in excess; masking agents are EDTA for Ni, Cu, Cd, fluoride for Fe, and tartarate for Pb. A 4 to 5-fold excess of U^{VI} , Cu^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pt^{IV} are tolerated; masking agents are EDTA for U, Cu, and KI for Hg and Pt is extracted first at 0.5 *N* HCl medium with chloroform (15 min heating on water-bath is required before extraction). A 1 to 3-fold presence are tolerated for Ru^{III} , Pd^{II} , Rh^{III} , $\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}/\text{Os}^{\text{VI}}$; the masking agent is NH_4OH for Ru^{III} . Rh^{III} interferes in the determination of iridium with DPyT. CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , EDTA, NH_2OH , I^- , SO_4^{2-} have no interference upto 500-fold excess.

Application : The proposed method was applied for the determination of Os^{VI} and Ir^{III} in binary mixtures of the two. Osmium was extracted first at pH 3.6 and then iridium was determined following the requisite condition. In binary mixture one where the osmium content is 100.0 μg and iridium conc. is 102.2 μg , the relative mean deviation is 0.1% for Os and 0.35% for Ir. In the mixture when the Os

and Ir contents are 50.0 and 51.1 μg respectively, the relative deviation for Os is 0.08 % and for Ir is 0.042%. The results are interpreted from 5 parallel set of determination.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss PMQII spectrophotometer with 1cm quartz cell was used. A Systronics 324 pH meter was used. IR spectra (KBr) were determined by a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer.

Standard Os^{VIII} solution was prepared by dissolving osmium tetroxide (J.M.) (1 g) in (0.2 *M*) sodium hydroxide solution and the volume was made up to 500 ml, and estimated by standard method⁶. To obtain Os^{VI} solution 1 : 2 (v/v) ethanol was added for reduction.

Ir^{III} solution was prepared by dissolving $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (J. M.) (1 g) (500 ml) and standardized^{1,7}. Solutions of other metals were prepared by dissolving their salts in distilled water or in dil. HCl. Dil. HCl and 10% sodium acetate solution were used for regulating pH of the solution.

Preparation of the reagent DPyT⁸ : Carbon disulfide (0.1 mol) and 2-aminopyridine (0.2 mol) in ethanol was mixed with little powdered potassium hydroxide pellets. The whole content was refluxed for 8 h on a water-bath, then excess CS_2 was distilled off and the residue shaken with dil. HCl and filtered. The cream coloured flower-like crystals were recrystallized from water-ethanol mixture, m.p. 146°.

A solution of this reagent (1×10^{-2} *M*) in spec-pure ethanol was used throughout the experiment. All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure for osmium : To an aliquot (1–2 ml) containing known amount of osmium ethanol was added and the mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min for reduction of the metal to its hexavalent state. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.6–5.8 using Na-acetate/HCl buffer. After addition of the reagent solution (1–2 ml), the mixture was heated for 15–20 min over a boiling water-bath. The resulting green solution was cooled to room temp. and extracted thrice with chloroform : ethanol mixture (4 : 1), then made up to 25 ml with the same solvent, dried over the anhyd. Na_2SO_4 and its absorbance was measured at 355 nm against the reagent blank.

Procedure for iridium : The pH of the Ir solution was adjusted to 5.0–6.4 with the buffer solution. After addition of the reagent solution (1–2 ml), the mixture was heated over a boiling water-bath for 40–45 min, then cooled to room temp. Subsequent extraction and absorbance measurements at 335 nm were the same as that for osmium.

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